

Understanding and Importance of Partnership of Internal Affairs Departments with Other Field Services and the Community in the Counter-Drug Department

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Abstract: This article reveals the nature and significance of the interaction between the operational units of the internal affairs bodies to combat narcotic drugs and other industry services and bodies carrying out activities to interact with the population. The article analyzes the concept, forms and stages of relationships, organizational and managerial aspects, the author's definition of the concept of "activities of other industry services and public cooperation in the fight against drugs of operational units of internal affairs bodies", as well as opportunities are formed as its effectiveness increases. The work uses a complex of general scientific and special scientific methods of cognition, including such methods as the systematic method, synthesis, analysis, induction and other methods of scientific research. The scientific novelty lies in a comprehensive analysis of the nature and content of interaction between operational units of internal affairs bodies with other industry services and the public in the fight against drugs. The main conclusion of the study is that the levels, forms and areas of cooperation between operational units of internal affairs bodies with other industry services and the public in the fight against drugs are closely related to each other and together constitute its main content.

Keywords: drugs, field services, public, types of cooperation, forms, operational departments.

MAIN PART

One of the factors that significantly influences the results of any team is the properly organized and skillfully implemented interaction between its participants.

Each government agency cannot ensure the effectiveness of its activities only within the limits of its internal capabilities without cooperation with other structures. [9, p. 11]

The concept of mutual cooperation in the fight against narcotic drugs of operational units of internal affairs agencies with other industry services and cooperation with the public can be understood on the basis of the general concept of mutual compatibility of any entities operating in society from the point of view of various fields.

Mutual cooperation between investigative bodies and the population is of fundamental importance for the protection of society and state security from criminal encroachments. The forms and directions of this mutual cooperation are seriously studied by modern scientists. Each of them confirms that an important potential for the fight against crime is hidden in the assistance of citizens to law enforcement agencies [1, pp. 36-40].

In philosophy, "interaction" is defined as a category reflecting the processes of influence of various objects on each other, their mutual conditioning and change of state. Interaction is an integrating factor, with the help of which parts are united into a certain whole [2, p. 394].

Also, interaction in the article under consideration is the process of interaction of operational units of the internal affairs bodies for combating drugs and other industry services and the population, in turn, their interdependence, interconnected activities are manifested, and the role of one subject in the fight against crime presupposes interdependence and coordination of activities. It should be noted that interaction serves as an integrating factor in the unification of the above-mentioned bodies into a single system, which in the process of their work change their position compared to the initial state. Based on the above, it can be assumed that interaction is a certain type of relationship between subjects solving common or interconnected problems, which can be called cooperation and is manifested in their joint or coordinated activities. That is, the essence of interaction is the interconnection of subjects.

The main goal of cooperation between operational investigation units and field services and the public in detecting and preventing drug-related crimes is to prove cases that are the subject of the investigation. It can be said that cooperation is a method of learning the objective truth about crime.

In our opinion, in this case, the form of mutual cooperation should be understood as a certain organizational and tactical basis for implementing the interaction of interacting bodies to solve the tasks of solving and preventing crimes.

Most authors of cooperation understand the unity of interrelated elements, each of which performs its own function, contributing to the achievement of a common goal. If we talk about mutual cooperation of operational units of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, they are an integral part of individual regional internal affairs bodies. If the subjects of interaction represent different departments, they are part of a single system of state bodies for combating crime. In our opinion, the interaction of operational units, operational services and public cooperation through the implementation of measures to solve and prevent drug crimes, forming an independent, albeit temporary system, is aimed at achieving final results, that is, they form a specific program-target structure.

Continuity of mutual cooperation is associated with the stability of the tasks facing the operational units of the field service and interaction with the public. The specified features of the interaction of operational investigation units, industry services and the public allow us to consider it as a specific process. International dictionaries define "cooperation" as a series of changes in circumstances or a series of actions to achieve a result. In relation to the labor process, cooperation is defined as a set of actions carried out in order to obtain a specific product of labor [3, p. 16]. In a practical sense, the content of the process of relations with the public and operational services of investigative bodies is a moving dynamic system, the components of which are coordinated and joint actions at certain stages of solving and preventing crimes.

A) Cooperation - (employee, colleague) 1. Someone who does work together. 2 - a mutually supportive employee willing to cooperate.

B) Cooperation - 1) to be a partner in work, to unite in one work, to do it equally. 2) joint work and joint work in the field [8, p. 309].

It should be noted that the interaction of subjects at any level requires organizational influence, which is understood as a targeted influence on achieving a certain goal.

The organization of mutual cooperation is essentially a management activity, or more precisely, social management. Social management is the influence of management subjects on a social system with the aim of directing it to the implementation of their goals and objectives. Depending on the current situation, the impact can be aimed at regulating the system, stabilizing it or transferring it to another state and is carried out through the correct organization and coordination of people's activities [4, p. 8].

Thus, an important factor in organizing mutual cooperation, as well as in its implementation, is the process of collecting, processing, transmitting and using information. Therefore, the system

of mutual informing of the bodies involved in the fight against crime is a necessary condition for ensuring their mutual cooperation.

When considering the legal regulation of cooperation between emergency services and industry services and the population, two important factors should be taken into account:

Firstly, the legal basis for mutual cooperation has now been significantly expanded. The laws "On operational-search activities" and "On internal affairs agencies" oblige operational-search activities to be carried out by operational units.

Secondly, the aforementioned laws clearly limit their powers in solving the problems of detecting and preventing crimes.

The international legal literature defines various forms of interaction between subjects of the fight against crime. At the same time, depending on the legal regulation, procedural and non-procedural forms of interaction are distinguished [5, p. 495].

Based on the above definitions, the following forms of interaction can be distinguished depending on legal regulation, methods of implementation and levels of interaction:

In accordance with the rules:

- procedural;
- non-procedural.

Cooperating with:

- joint or coordinated work;
- information exchange.

By levels of interaction:

- organizational and managerial;
- organizational and tactical.

According to V. M. Shvankov, the most important signs of interaction are the following:

- cooperation;
- mutual assistance;
- interaction of forces and means;
- increase the "resolution" of the system;
- strengthening its control parameters [6, p. 10].

Both of these approaches to defining "interaction" are scientifically substantiated. However, it seems to us that in the first case, showing joint or coordinated actions in terms of goals, place and time, the main attention is paid to the appearance of interaction, i.e. priority is given to describing the form. In the second case, on the contrary, attention is paid to the essence of this phenomenon, emphasizing that interaction is cooperation based on support.

In his research, Professor I. Ismailov conditionally divided cooperation in the system of combating crime into four areas;

- Intradepartmental cooperation
- Interdepartmental cooperation
- Cooperation with the public
- International cooperation [7, p. 30].

Mutual cooperation begins at the request of a regulatory legal document or at the initiative of one of the parties.

The main stage is the stage of actual coordinated or joint activity.

The final stage is the stage of assessing the effectiveness of the work performed and summing up the results.

Achieving high consistency serves to increase the effectiveness of the operational search departments in the field of field service and interaction with the public. However, due to the extreme diversity of methods for committing even one type of crime, the consistency of functional and role expectations can only be achieved at the organizational and managerial level and cannot be achieved in advance at the operational and tactical level. Therefore, interacting entities must be psychologically prepared to act in a coordinated manner in uncertain conditions.

Cooperation is conventionally divided into two main forms;

- Mutual exchange of information;
- Divided into practical cooperation, which is manifested in joint planning of specific measures of activity, generalization of the results of implementation, mutual assistance and support for the implementation of certain tasks [10, p. 13].

Thus, it seems that we can come to the following conclusion. The studied levels, forms and directions of interaction, with all their diversity, are closely related to each other and together constitute its main content. This cooperation is a joint activity based on laws and legal documents, each of the cooperating parties uses its own special powers, methods and forms, and the main direction of activity is to find the person who committed the crime and reliably prove his guilt so that the court will assign him a fair punishment.

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